

MODERN GAMING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE CLASSROOM RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: This article discusses modern gaming technologies in Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities. The use of innovative technologies in the lessons of Russian as a foreign language is one of the conditions for organizing the modern educational process for the effective acquisition of lexical and grammatical knowledge and the development of students' communicative abilities. Conducting classes in a playful way, using game exercises at different stages of the lesson is organic and corresponds to the realities of the modern information society. Among the gaming technologies, teachers highlight storytelling, hackathon, education, board, communicative, interactive games and others, which are implemented through the methods of role-playing interaction, practice-oriented, problem-based and adaptive learning. Gaming technologies are aimed at developing the speech skills of students at non-linguistic universities and their creative activity, maintaining student interest, reducing information overload and psychological stress, and promoting memorization of lexical and grammatical material in an entertaining way.

Keywords: gaming technologies, storytelling, hackathon, educational science, board games, communicative games, interactive games, computer games, Russian language.

1 INTRODUCTION

The modern information society places demand on the organization of the educational process, in which innovative technologies contribute to the formation of positive motivation and the development of cognitive interest in learning the Russian language. Among the innovative technologies used in Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities, attention is paid to problem-based learning technologies, level differentiation, information and communication, design and research, student-oriented, gaming [4], communication, individualized learning technologies, computer testing, distance educational technologies, mastered by students in a foreign language environment independently [1].

The concept of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities is based on a communicative approach, which allows you to freely construct correct speech statements, taking into account the roles of communicants and the situation in which communication takes place. In order to best achieve your educational goal, you must strive to fulfill the following conditions:

- take into account the social, cultural and psychological characteristics of the educational process;
- create interactive learning situations to activate students' mental activity and maintain their interest;
- the lesson material must correspond to the level of training of foreigners and be aimed at developing

sociocultural literacy for the successful solution of communicative tasks in accordance with the situation;

- balance traditional and new types of work.

2 Materials and methods

The material for the analysis was articles by teachers devoted to the consideration of gaming technologies. Presenting a non-standard form of organization of learning, they attract the attention of students from non-linguistic universities, because they help to implement the educational task in a relaxed atmosphere with an entertaining presentation of the material.

To summarize the best linguodidactic experience, publications in scientific electronic libraries were used. The search was carried out using the main words: gaming technologies. Then, repeated queries were made in the resulting samples, the keywords of which were Russian as a foreign language and non-linguistic universities. The results of the search queries allowed us to obtain 150 works devoted to the use of gaming technologies in Russian language lessons in various specialties [2,5,6,7]. Having analyzed these works, we came to the conclusion that teachers turned to the study of the topic of gaming technologies in foreign language lessons in 2014 in a global context. In Uzbekistan, the widespread use of gaming technologies began in 2020, and since 2023, articles on this topic have almost doubled in the number of articles published in electronic scientific publications by Uzbek researchers (Fig. 1).

All these data indicate a growing interest among teachers in the topic of using gaming technologies in Russian language lessons in non-linguistic universities.

This article aims to identify modern gaming technologies that are popular among Russian language teachers, and to describe the features of their implementation among students at non-linguistic universities.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the analysis of scientific and methodological developments, the following was established. One of the modern game technologies for teaching the Russian language at non-linguistic universities is edutainment. The English term edutainment is a portmanteau of the initial and final parts of the two words education and entertainment.

The specificity of the technology, which can be implemented both with and without the use of multimedia, lies in practice-oriented learning, during which students participate in life situations, enrich their own experience and learn behavioral skills. The control system is changing: students are given greater freedom of expression and creative work is encouraged. The relationship between a teacher and a student is built not along a vertical line (teacher - student), but along a horizontal line, where the student acts as an active participant in the educational process of acquiring knowledge.

The positive potential of edutainment technology is to provide comfortable psychological conditions in the classroom, which are achieved through the use of three components:

Despite the advantages of the technology, there are also negative aspects of the use of edutainment, including the financial cost of implementing software, educational literature, the unrealistic nature of the input material due to the entertainment component [7], the automaticity of actions as a last resort means of conveying information when other effective methods no longer work [6]. Thus, when incorporating gaming technologies into your work, it is important to maintain the golden mean and not replace education with entertainment.

M. Akhmedova includes traditional (video films, songs, educational games, books, comics) and modern means of education, among which are computer technologies (electronic interactive textbooks, computer games, electronic simulators) and Internet technologies (web quests, blogs, chats, video podcasts, audio podcasts, multimedia online courses) [1].

Teachers of the Russian language in non-linguistic universities who implement education turn to regional material and offer students interactive web applications, for example, “A Walk-through Eternal Tashkent” [3], which can also be launched on mobile devices. The electronic simulator contains the main topics that are related to moving around the city and relate to the use of transport services, visiting remarkable places in the cultural and educational center of the city: the university, the aquarium, the Ilkhom Theater, Victory Park, Ecopark, A. Temur Museum. Quest tasks and listening tasks, in which students need to choose words related or, conversely, not related to any location, determine the grammatical categories of gender, animateness / inanimateness, allow them to test the development of lexical, grammatical and auditing skills.

Teachers offer games for bilingual children and students learning Russian at the initial stage that allow them to get to know each other and unite the team: “Snowball”, “Alphabet of Names”, “Let’s Talk”, “Business Card”; work on lexical and grammatical material: ball games based on the “edible/inedible” principle; “Associative classics” on the board, when they get into the box of which the student must name the largest number of words on a certain topic; organize communication: carry out project tasks related to history, culture, science; participation in role-playing games close to real communicative conditions [2].

At the University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, in the 1st year, the storytelling method is used, the essence of which is viewing, reading, retelling entertaining, funny mini-plots, as well as playing out any constructions in different situations. Both specially developed educational texts and video fragments, as well as authentic, but significantly abbreviated ones, are

used as material for the narration [4]. This type of work allows students to improve their pronunciation, expand their vocabulary, and develop communication skills. An audio recording of the voiced text by the student and a test reading of the text by the teacher contribute to the mastery of pronunciation skills.

In the correspondence course, teachers implement the multimedia game “Spin the Wheel.” The game is built by analogy with the TV game “Field of Miracles” and is designed using Powerpoint. The great possibilities provided by computer technology make it possible to combine text, graphic data, music, and video. To play the game, the group was divided into 2 teams, each participant of which spun the wheel and received the right to complete the game task: conjugate verbs, deflect nouns, fill in the missing places, and restore the text. The sectors of the improvised wheel are numbered and marked with numbers corresponding to the question numbers. Each player had to guess the word or phrase as quickly as possible and get points. If the group found it difficult to answer, then the turn passed to the other team; if the player failed to complete the task by indicating the wrong word, he was eliminated; the participant who reached the final was declared the winner [7].

Teachers note that teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities with the help of computer games helps psychologically prepare students for independent learning. G. Musaeva proposes a project of a communication-oriented electronic educational resource on Russian as a foreign language using v-learning technology. In the context of distance learning of the Russian language, virtual reality technologies provide immersion in a virtual language environment based on social interaction. Computer-mediated communication, which is implemented in multi-user virtual worlds, helps to more successfully learn the Russian language, increase students’ motivation, and involve them in the game process due to “visuality and the effect of immersion in what is happening” [5].

Users can participate in collaborative work and hold virtual conferences. Thus, organizing an educational process in which foreign students can realize almost all their communicative needs and demonstrate creative abilities allows them to successfully achieve educational goals.

In the methodology of teaching the Russian language, it is necessary to use technologies that are relevant for the present time. Among these, teachers note “problem-based learning technologies, information and communication, design and research, personality-oriented, gaming, level differentiation technologies” [3].

The period of the coronavirus pandemic led to a change in the usual work formats, when, in conditions of physical distancing and social isolation in educational institutions, it was necessary to develop a new form of interaction - computer-mediated.

O.G. Glazova, in the process of distance work with history students proficient in Russian foreign language at levels B2, C1, attracted popular science films “Nine Days and the Whole Life”, “So that they Live!”, “Recipe for Victory. Medicine during the Great Patriotic War”, which have not only educational, cognitive, but also communicative and diagnostic potential [3]. The result of the use of video materials was the enrichment of foreign speakers with linguistic and cultural information, training in discussion, and the production of written texts in the form of essays.

Kh. Valieva turns to a didactic computer game as a multimedia educational technology that contributes to the intensification of the educational process, and uses the sites <https://learningapps.org>, <http://www.classtools.ru>, ISpring program. Computer games can be offered as distance learning tools:

- 1) with an adventure plot, the characters of which perform some tasks, where, using the example of a horse racing game in which the second participant is a computer or a player, you need to choose the correct answer on the topic “Symbols of Russia”;
- 2) with puzzles in which you need to logically arrange something, find matches, solve a problem (for example, from pictures related to the highlighted word, assemble a puzzle on the topic “Emotions”);
- 3) with word games in which you need to find words, solve a crossword, puzzle, anagram, rebus, etc.;
- 4) with board and card games [4].

The study by M. V. Kholodkova, Zh. I. Zherebtsova, T. A. Dyakova shows that most of the traditional gaming techniques that have become familiar in face-to-face work can be practiced during distance learning to form and develop the competencies of foreign students. Thus, for honing lexical skills, the online services Wordwall, Flippity, Quizlet are recommended, as well as tasks for working with anagram recognition, finding words in fillwords, solving crossword puzzles, searching for matches, grouping words, identifying objects in a picture, lotto, board games can be offered walking games; virtual boards Miro, Google Jamboard, Google Drawings, Google Slides are used to develop phonetic skills; for the formation of grammatical skills - language, speech grammar games, simulators in flash card format, prepared with the assistance of Flippity; for the development of communicative competence - online service for producing comics Storyboardthat; linguistic and cultural studies - electronic quizzes on the online

services Wordwall, Flippity, Kahoot!, QuizWhizzer, Doozy, Triventy [7].

Despite the existing scientific and practical works devoted to the use of online services in face-to-face classes, a small part of the work examines the issues of introducing gaming technologies using Web 2.0 tools when conducting Russian language classes remotely in non-linguistic universities. The transition from Web 1.0 to Web 2.0 resources was marked by a change in the role of users of information services: from a consumer of content studying, analyzing, perceiving text, graphics, videos posted on sites, a person becomes a co-author and producer of information material, carrying out network interaction.

Modern technical means allow for new forms of contact and interpersonal communication. In the methodology of teaching the Russian language in non-linguistic universities, a hackathon becomes such a means of social interaction. This new designation is literally translated as a hacker marathon and is a combination of the initial and final parts of the lexemes hacker ('hacker') and marathon ('marathon') and denotes a competition in which the participating teams need to solve a problem in a limited time.

In the pedagogical activities of modern university teachers, team educational and cognitive games are used to teach students Russian as a second language from neighboring countries in collaboration with Russian students, which colleagues conduct in the hackathon format using case technologies. They carry out the educational process by turning to the methods of role-playing interaction, practice-oriented and adaptive learning [6]. The result of team collaboration is a new educational linguistic product with lexical and grammatical topics of the Russian language, developed by student groups together, taking into account the characteristics of national mentalities and proficiency levels of Uzbek students.

Game tasks are built on the principle of increasing complexity. The implementation of the hackathon takes place in three stages [1], which can be classified as independent study, control, and teaching.

1. Team players receive cases with theoretical and practical information on any lexical and grammatical topic, presented with reference tables and tables for entering data, the cells of which they fill out by moving objects.

2. Team members are given the results of checking their answers. Students can redo the assignment, asking a team member for help if necessary. Points are awarded for speed, but a team does not receive a game point if it does not show empathy for its team's lagging players.

3. There is a change of roles: the participants of the two teams must transfer their knowledge to each other, that is, act as teachers. To carry out a responsible mission, those means that mentor players consider the most optimal for conveying information can be used. This type of collaboration is at the same time analytical, communicative and creative, it allows you to study the topic in a playful way in practice, since before acting as a teacher, the student himself must understand it well.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Scientific and methodological publications actively discuss the issues of attracting gaming technologies to non-linguistic students in Russian language lessons, the fundamental principles of which are visualization, interactivity, changing types of activities, multimedia support, and communicative orientation.

Training taking into account the competency-based approach, in which the student must be ready to solve life and professional problems, the practical application of knowledge, skills and abilities, is aimed at developing linguistic, speech and communicative competencies that are combined with sociocultural competence. In the practice of Russian language teachers in non-linguistic universities, regional linguistic and regional material is used, which allows students to acquaint themselves with the urban environment, the way of life of the people, introduce them to the culture of the country of the language being studied, and learn about traditions.

Turning to computer technology provides ample opportunities for recreating a virtual language environment in which the student acts as an active user, receives knowledge and transfers it to others, working in a hackathon format. Participation in group games, on the one hand, acts as a motivator for completing a gaming educational task, and on the other, it develops team spirit and cooperation skills, where everyone works for the group, which unites the student body.

Honing pronunciation skills is facilitated by the storytelling method, thanks to which foreign speakers learn to listen to themselves, relate their speech to a model, develop vocabulary, and train their memory.

Despite the concept of learning through entertainment, not all teachers tend to see positive potential in education. When implementing gaming technologies, you should consider the balance between entertainment and learning.

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